

ON THE DIVISORS OF SMARANDACHE UNARY SEQUENCE

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ABSTRACT: Smarandache Unary Sequence is defined as follows:

$u(n) = 1111 \dots$, p_n digits of "1", where p_n is the n^{th} prime.

11, 111, 11111, 1111111 \dots

Are there an infinite number of primes in this sequence? It is still an unsolved problem. The following property of a divisor of $u(n)$ is established.

If 'd' is a divisor of $u(n)$ then $d \equiv 1 \pmod{p_n}$, for all $n > 3$ ---(1),

DESCRIPTION: Let $l(m) = 1111 \dots$ m times $= (10^m - 1) / 9$

Then $u(n) = l(p_n)$.

Following proposition will be applied to establish (1).

Proposition : $l(p-1) \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$.-----(2)

PROOF: 9 divides $10^{p-1} - 1$. From Fermat's little theorem if $p \geq 7$ is a prime then p divides $(10^{p-1} - 1) / 9$

as $(p, 9) = (p, 10) = 1$. Hence p divides $l(p-1)$

Coming back to the main proposition, let 'd' be a divisor of $u(n)$.

Let $d = p^a q^b r^c \dots$, where p, q, r , are prime factors of d .

p divides 'd' $\Rightarrow p$ divides $u(n)$ also p divides $l(p-1)$ from proposition (2). in other words

p divides $(10^{p-1} - 1) / 9$ and p divides $(10^p - 1) / 9$

p divides $(10^{A(p-1)} - 1) / 9$ and p divides $(10^{B \cdot p} - 1) / 9$

p divides $(10^{(A(p-1) - B \cdot p)}) / 9$

p divides $10^{B \cdot p} \{ (10^{A(p-1) - B \cdot p} - 1) / 9 \}$.

p divides $(10^{A(p-1) - B \cdot p} - 1) / 9$. -----(3)

There exist A and B such that

$A(p - 1) - B.p_n = (p - 1, p_n)$. As p_n is a prime there are two possibilities :

(i). $(p - 1, p_n) = 1$ or (ii). $(p - 1, p_n) = p_n$.

In the first case , from (3) we get p divides $(10 - 1)/9$ or p

divides 1, which is absurd as $p > 1$. hence $(p - 1, p_n) = p_n$:
or p_n divides $p - 1$

$$p \equiv 1 \pmod{p_n}$$

$$\Rightarrow p^a \equiv 1 \pmod{p_n}$$

on similar lines

$$q^b \equiv 1 \pmod{p_n}$$

$$\text{hence } d = p^a q^b r^c \dots \equiv 1 \pmod{p_n}$$

This completes the proof.

COROLLARY : For any prime p there exists at least one prime q such that
 $q \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$

Proof: As $u(n) \equiv 1 \pmod{p_n}$, and also every divisor of $u(n)$ is

$\equiv 1 \pmod{p_n}$, the corollary stands proved. Also clearly such a 'q' is greater than p , this gives us a proof of the infinitude of the prime numbers as a by product.

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